

Metal ion interaction with tridentate ONO donor azo ligands : Part I. Equilibrium study on the complex formation of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with azo ligands

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Abstract : The ionization constants of three ONO donor azo ligands (H_2L^{1-3}) containing different functional groups, viz. 2-hydroxy-2'-carboxy-5-methylazobenzene (H_2L^1), 2,2'-dihydroxyazobenzene (H_2L^2) and 2-hydroxy-2'-hydroxymethyl-5-methylazobenzene (H_2L^3) and their formation constants with M^{2+} ions ($\text{M} = \text{Co}, \text{Ni}, \text{Cu}$ and Zn) have been determined in dioxane-water (50% v/v) medium at 25 °C at a fixed ionic strength ($I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NaNO}_3$) by pH-potentiometric method. The nature of the species present in solution have been elucidated on the basis of their electronic spectra. Job's method of continuous variation study indicated the formation of 1 : 1 complex with Cu^{2+} ion and 1 : 2 complex with Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions with all these three ligands. Formation constants of these metal ions with all these three ligands have been found to follow the order : $\text{Co}^{2+} < \text{Ni}^{2+} < \text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+}$. With respect to any particular metal ion, the formation constant values follow the order : $(\text{L}^1)^{2-} < (\text{L}^2)^{2-} < (\text{L}^3)^{2-}$ which is explained on the basis of overall basicity of these ligands.

Keywords : Formation constants, cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II), zinc(II), azo ligands.

Introduction

Azo compounds play an important role in analytical chemistry as chromogenic agents¹. From the biological point of view, the study of the binding properties of organic chelating ligands containing the functional groups with dissociable protons (viz. COOH, OH, CH_2OH etc.) at one of the two α -positions with respect to azo nitrogen atoms in both the aromatic rings (Scheme 1) is significant due to their use as models for certain metal-enzyme interactions and also for the possible transport of metal ions in biological media²⁻⁵ resulting from the formation of charge neutral metal complexes with bivalent metal ions. It has also been proved that polydentate chelating agents can remove the metal ions from metalloenzymes through the formation of ternary complexes between the metal, the ligand and the apoenzyme. The inhibition of carbonic anhydrase by actazolamide, which is able to bind Zn^{2+} ion is an example of such type⁶. From the physiological point of view, azo compounds particularly the H_2L^1 have some antibacterial property⁷. As a part of our programme on the equilibrium study of the complex formation of

biologically relevant bivalent metal ions (viz. Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+}) with dibasic ONO donor azo ligands, we have used three such ligands, viz. 2-hydroxy-2'-carboxy-5-methylazobenzene (H_2L^1), 2,2'-dihydroxy-

H_2L (I)

H_2L	R
H_2L^1	COOH
H_2L^2	OH
H_2L^3	CH_2OH

Scheme 1

azobenzene (H_2L^2) and 2-hydroxy-2'-hydroxymethyl-5-methylazobenzene (H_2L^3) (general abbreviation H_2L , I). To the best of our knowledge, practically no equilibrium study have been done with such type of ligands except a spectrophotometric study for the determination of stability constants of the complexes formed by some bivalent metal ions with H_2L^1 in DMF solution⁷. Due to the insolubility of azo-ligands in water, the potentiometric study of these compounds require the use of an organic or aquo-organic solvent where these complexes have appreciable solubility and which presents compatibility with the standard glass electrode. In this context, a 50% v/v dioxane-water mixture has been reported to be a suitable solvent for the solution study of such type of azo compounds⁸.

Results and discussion

Proton-ligand equilibria :

All these azo donor ligands (H_2L^{1-3} , general abbreviation H_2L , I) have a tendency to accept one proton in acidic medium due to the protonation in one of the two azo N-atoms and should behave as tribasic acids (H_3L^+). But the protonated forms titrated as diprotic acids in the absence of metal ion and offered two buffer regions between pH 2.0–3.0 and pH 5.0–6.0 for H_2L^1 due to deprotonation of $=NH^+$ and $-COOH$ groups, respectively, whereas for $H_2L^{2,3}$ ligands, the buffer regions are pH 2.5–3.5 and pH 10.5–11.5, respectively for the deprotonation of $=NH^+$ and PhOH moieties. The reluctance of the third protonic group viz. PhOH or CH_2OH for undergoing deprotonation is probably partly due to their strong basicity and partly due to the formation of intramolecular H-bond with the dissociated $-COO^-$ or PhO^- moiety. Due to the presence of higher acidic $-COOH$ group in H_2L^1 , this ligand may also be present as a zwitterions of the type $(H^+)(HL^1)^-$. Proton ligand constants are collected in Table 1. Hydrolysis constants of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions have been determined under the experimental condition and are collected in Table 2.

Table 1. Deprotonation constants^a of the ligands in 50% v/v aqueous-dioxane solution at 25 °C with an ionic strength $I = 0.1 M NaNO_3$

Constant	H_2L^1	H_2L^2	H_2L^3
$pK_{LH_3}^H$	2.01	3.02	3.02
$pK_{LH_2}^H$	5.23	10.70	10.70
pK_{LH}^H	10.70	11.65	12.50

^aLimits of error in the constants : ± 0.02 in log units.

Metal-ligand equilibria :

The complex formation equilibria for Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions with all these three ligands are very much similar and for this reason an elaborate discussion with one ligand system is sufficient to represent the equilibria with the other two ligand systems also.

Complex formation of H_2L^1 with Cu^{2+} ion was observed at $pH \geq 3.5$, where the ligand is present predominantly in the H_2L form. A plot of pH vs volume of NaOH solution added for $Cu^{2+}-H_2L^1$ system (Fig. 1) indicates that two H^+ per Cu^{2+} were released between pH 3.5 and 7.5 in two overlapping steps. At pH 5.0, the 1 : 3 $Cu^{2+} : H_2L^1$ mixture exhibited absorption peak at 508 nm due to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition. On increasing the pH to ~ 7.6 , no significant change in λ_{max} value was observed. Job's method of continuous variation⁹ study at pH 5.0 and 7.6 of this system indicated the formation of only 1 : 1 complex in solution. Buffer regions corresponding to metal-ligand complexation equilibria were observed (Fig. 1) at pH values much lower than those of the hydrolytic equilibria of $M^{2+}(aq.)$ ions. Therefore, simple hydroxo spe-

cies are less likely to occur. However, at higher pH values the occurrence of ternary metal-ligand-hydroxo complexes and also some simple hydroxo species could not be ruled out. Therefore, the species H_3L^+ , H_2L , HL^- , L^{2-} , Cu^{2+} , $Cu(OH)^+$, $Cu(OH)_2$, $CuL(H_2O)$ and $CuL(OH)^-$ were considered in calculating the metal-ligand formation constants.

III

Table 2. Hydrolysis constants^a of M²⁺ (aq.) ions and metal-ligand constants^a with H₂L¹, H₂L² and H₂L³ in 50% v/v aqueous-dioxane solution at 25 °C with an ionic strength *I* = 0.1 M NaNO₃

Constant	Co ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Zn ²⁺
pK ^H _M	8.18	7.82	6.98	8.47
pK ^{2H} _M	17.07	16.28	12.95	13.77
log K ^M _{ML¹(H₂O)_{1 or 3}}	7.39	7.46	10.09	6.52
log K ^M _{M(L¹)₂}	10.06	10.25	-	-
pK ^H _{ML¹(H₂O)}	-	-	12.09	14.86
log K ^M _{ML²(H₂O)_{1 or 3}}	8.52	9.08	14.05	7.64
log K ^M _{M(L²)₂}	15.06	17.50	-	-
pK ^H _{ML²(H₂O)}	-	-	13.05	14.03
log K ^M _{ML³(H₂O)_{1 or 3}}	9.84	11.04	16.98	8.42
log K ^M _{M(L³)₂}	16.73	19.86	-	-
pK ^H _{ML³(H₂O)}	-	-	14.21	18.36

^aLimits of error in the constants : ± 0.02-0.04 in log units.

From the distribution profiles of Cu²⁺ and H₂L¹ system (Fig. 2a) it appeared that the complex [CuL¹(H₂O)] was formed according to the following equilibrium :

$K^{\text{Cu}}_{\text{CuL}^1(\text{H}_2\text{O})} = [\text{Cu}(\text{L}^1)(\text{H}_2\text{O})]/([\text{Cu}][\text{L}^1][\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ (1) which involved the substitution of -COOH and PhOH protons respectively. Charges are omitted for clarity. The observed λ_{max} (508 nm) of the Cu²⁺-H₂L¹ mixture at

Fig. 1. A representative curve of pH vs volume of NaOH solution added for Cu²⁺-H₂L¹ system : (1) 0.01 M HNO₃; (2) 1 + 0.001 M Cu(NO₃)₂; (3) 1 + 0.003 M (H₃L¹); (4) 3 + 0.001 M Cu²⁺.

pH ~5.0 and pH ~7.6 corresponding to the formation of maximum amount of metal-ligand binary species was close to the calculated¹⁰ value (510 nm) for a square-planar copper complex in which the Cu²⁺ ion is coordinated by a carboxylate-oxygen atom, an azo nitrogen atom, a phenolate-oxygen atom and the oxygen of a water molecule. It is, therefore, obvious that Cu²⁺ ion in the [Cu(L¹)(H₂O)] complex was coordinated by the carboxylate-oxygen, azo-nitrogen and phenolate-oxygen of deprotonated H₂L¹ and took up one water molecule to have a square planar geometry (II). Such type of meridional disposition of (L¹)²⁻ species is X-ray crystallographically well established¹¹. From the Fig. 2(a), it is obvious that the [Cu(L¹)(H₂O)] complex is formed to the extent of ~98% of total copper at pH ~5 and almost such a concentration is maintained upto pH 8. At pH > 8, the concentration of this complex sharply decreases to ~55% at pH ~9.5 and the concentration of Cu(OH)₂ sharply increases resulting its precipitation. The ternary hydroxo

Fig. 2. (a) Species distribution curves of Cu²⁺-H₂L¹ system at different pH : (1) [H₃L¹]⁺; (2) H₂L¹; (3) [HL¹]⁻; (4) M(OH)⁺; (5) M(OH)₂; (6) [ML¹(H₂O)]; (7) [ML¹(OH)]⁻. (b) Species distribution curves of Cu²⁺-H₂L² system at different pH : (1) [H₃L²]⁺; (2) H₂L²; (3) [HL²]⁻; (4) M(OH)⁺; (5) M(OH)₂; (6) [ML²(H₂O)]; (7) [M(L²)₂]²⁻.

$[\text{Cu}(\text{L}^1)(\text{OH})]^-$ complex therefore, resulted from the deprotonation of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L}^1)(\text{OH}_2)]$ complex according to the following equilibrium :

The possible equilibrium for the formation of $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ from the decomposition of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L}^1)(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ may be :

Almost negligible concentration ($< 1\%$) of ternary metal-ligand-hydroxo species was observed which, could not even be identified in the species distribution curves (Fig. 2a) indicating the reluctance for deprotonation of the coordinated water molecule. This is probably due to the absence of any vacant orbital (π -acceptor) of the coordinated atom, which can delocalise the accumulated negative charge on Cu^{2+} ion as a result of deprotonation.

The complexation equilibria of H_2L^1 with Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions were observed at $\text{pH} \geq 5.0$ which is at slightly higher pH value than with Cu^{2+} ion. The plots of pH vs volume of NaOH solution added with Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions also indicated the release of two H^+ ions per M^{2+} ion like Cu^{2+} ion between pH 5 and 10. The 1 : 3 $\text{Co}^{2+} : \text{H}_2\text{L}^1$ mixture exhibited three λ_{max} values at 624 nm, 405 nm and 385 nm due to ${}^3T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^3T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively at pH 7.6. Similarly, the 1 : 3 $\text{Ni}^{2+} : \text{H}_2\text{L}^1$ mixture also exhibited three λ_{max} values at 502 nm, 405 nm and 387 nm respectively, due to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions at pH 7.6. The Job's method of continuous variation study for $\text{Co}^{2+}-\text{H}_2\text{L}^1$ and $\text{Ni}^{2+}-\text{H}_2\text{L}^1$ systems at pH 7.6 indicated the formation of 1 : 2 complexes for each of these two systems. So, $[\text{M}(\text{L}^1)_2]^{2-}$ species is also considered in addition to the other species described earlier for calculating the metal-ligand formation constants. The distribution profiles of $\text{Co}^{2+}-\text{H}_2\text{L}^1$ and $\text{Ni}^{2+}-\text{H}_2\text{L}^1$ systems are very much similar and the complexation occurs at $\text{pH} \geq 5$, where the ligand is predominantly in the HL^- form and the complexes are formed according to the following equilibria :

$$K^{\text{M}}_{\text{M}(\text{L}^1)_2} = \frac{[\text{M}(\text{L}^1)_2]}{[\text{M}][\text{L}^1]^2} \quad (5)$$

where $\text{M}^{2+} = \text{Co}^{2+}$ or Ni^{2+} and the most probable gross structure of these $[\text{M}(\text{L}^1)_2]^{2-}$ complexes will be as designated by (III). It is, however, reasonable to assume the formation of 1 : 1 complex with Zn^{2+} ion like Cu^{2+} ion and for this system, complex formation started at $\text{pH} > 6.0$. Distribution profiles of $\text{Co}^{2+}-\text{H}_2\text{L}^2$ system are shown in Fig. 2(b). The stability constant data of these metal ions with all these three ligands have been collected in Table 2. An analysis of the stability constant values indicates the order : $\text{Co}^{2+} < \text{Ni}^{2+} < \text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+}$ for any particular ligand and $(\text{L}^1)^{2-} < (\text{L}^2)^{2-} < (\text{L}^3)^{2-}$ for any particular metal ion.

Experimental

Materials and reagents :

The ligands H_2L^{1-3} were prepared as previously described, using standard procedures¹³⁻¹⁵. Their purities were checked by elemental analysis and by ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectral studies. Freshly prepared solutions in 50% v/v dioxane-water of the ligands were always used. Stock solutions of about 0.01 M of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} were prepared by dissolving the corresponding nitrates (A.R. grade) in doubly distilled carbonate-free water and the solutions were made acidic by adding appreciable amount of HNO_3 to prevent metal hydrolysis. These solutions were standardized by ion-exchange separation combined with acid-base and complexometric titrations¹⁶. Carbonate-free NaOH solution in 50% v/v dioxane-water was used as the titrant. Dioxane was purified by the reported method¹⁷.

Potentiometric and spectrophotometric equipment :

Potentiometric titrations were carried out at 25.0 ± 0.1 °C, with the ionic strength (I) adjusted to 0.1 M NaNO_3 . pH measurements were carried out with a Systronics 335 digital pH-meter (accuracy ± 0.01 pH) employing a special glass electrode (pH 1-14) in conjugation with a saturated calomel electrode (SCE). The pH meter was standardized with the buffer solutions at two pH points viz. pH 4.0 and pH 7.0. The term pH in this work is defined as $-\log [\text{H}^+]$. pK_w of water at the experimental condition was obtained from the literature¹⁸. Equilibrium pH values were determined at every incremental addition of NaOH to the experimental solutions. Electronic spectra

were recorded on a Hitachi U-3501 spectrophotometer. ^1H NMR spectra of the ligands were recorded either in DMSO or in CDCl_3 solutions on a Bruker AM 300L (300 MHz) superconducting FT NMR spectrophotometer. A Perkin-Elmer CHNS/O analyzer 2400 was employed to obtain micro analytical data.

Equilibrium measurements : The following mixtures (initial volume 25 ml) were prepared for the equilibrium measurements.

- (i) 0.01 M HNO_3
- (ii) (i) + 0.001 M $\text{M}(\text{NO}_3)_2$
- (iii) (i) + 0.003 M H_3L^+
- (iv) (iii) + 0.001 M $\text{M}(\text{NO}_3)_2$

Requisite volume of 1 M NaNO_3 solution and purified dioxane were added to each solution to have fixed ionic strength, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaNO_3) and 50% v/v water-dioxane composition respectively. All the mixtures were allowed to attain equilibrium at the experimental temperature and were titrated pH-metrically with carbonate free 0.1 M NaOH solution prepared in 50% v/v water-dioxane.

Calculation of formation constants : Proton-ligand and metal-ligand constants of binary complexes were calculated using the SCOGS computer programme¹⁹⁻²¹. Considering the deprotonation constants of the ligands and the hydrolysis constants of M^{2+} (aq) ions, the following species were considered to exist in the complexation equilibria : H_3L^+ , H_2L , HL^- , L^{2-} , $\text{M}(\text{OH})^+$, $\text{M}(\text{OH})_2$, ML , ML_2^{2-} , $\text{ML}(\text{OH})^+$. Complexation equilibria have been elucidated on the basis of speciation curves (Fig. 2) obtained as computer outputs.

Conclusion :

This study indicates that Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions form only 1 : 1 complex with all these three ligands whereas 1 : 2 complexes are formed by Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions. This is due to the preferred octahedral geometry by the latter two ions in comparison to the preference of square planar geometry by Cu^{2+} ion or tetrahedral geometry by Zn^{2+} ion. In each of the three ligand systems, the stability constant values follow the Irving-Williams order. However, for a particular metal ion, the stability constant values follow the order : $(\text{L}^1)^{2-} < (\text{L}^2)^{2-} < (\text{L}^3)^{2-}$ which is in accordance with the overall basicity of these three ligands.

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